

Spectrophotometric determination of selegiline hydrochloride in bulk and in pharmaceutical formulations

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Abstract : A simple, accurate, reproducible and cost effective spectrophotometric method has been developed for the estimation of selegiline hydrochloride in bulk form and pharmaceutical formulations. The drug was highly soluble in water, so it was selected as a solvent for its estimation. For UV spectrophotometric method, maximum absorption was obtained at 209 nm. The developed method was validated with respect to specificity, precision, linearity and accuracy. The analysis data has been subjected to statistical analysis and the results of this study are validated. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range of 5 to 30 µg/ml with linear equation of $Y = 0.0245x + 0.0966$ with correlation coefficient of 0.9981.

Keywords : Spectrophotometric method, selegiline hydrochloride, linearity, Beer's law.

Introduction

Selegiline hydrochloride is white crystalline powder with chemical formula $C_{13}H_{18}NCl$ and molecular weight 223.74 g/mol. It is chemically known as (*R*)-*N*-methyl-*N*-(1-phenylpropan-2-yl)prop-1-yn-3-amine. It is a selective, irreversible inhibitor of monoamine oxidase (MAO-A). It is used to alleviate the symptoms of Parkinson's disease and also used as antidepressant¹. It is useful in veterinary medicine to treat Cushing's disease in dogs and it is also useful in treatment of cocaine addiction². Further, increase in the dosage of selegiline more than 10 mg/day may lead to the non-selective inhibition of MAO³. Minor side effects such as headache, dizziness and nausea have been reported during monotherapy, while severe effects including mortality have been reported when selegiline and levodopa or pethidine were administered together. Thus the contaminant use of these drugs is not recommended⁴. Hence, it is necessary to develop a standard method for the determination of selegiline in bulk and in pharmaceutical formulations.

The literature survey reveals that there are very few methods are reported for its estimation in bulk and in pharmaceutical formulations. Capillary electrophoresis was

applied for the separation of racemic mixture of selegiline^{5,6}, but no quantitative and validation data were included. An indirect enzymatic assay with fluorescence detection⁷ and spectrophotometric method based on oxidation followed by coupling² were reported but these methods involve several tedious and time consuming steps. A GC-MS approach⁸ was reported but requires synthesis of a deuterated internal standard is required.

The aim of this study is to develop a simple, sensitive, accurate, cost effective and reproducible method for the estimation of selegiline hydrochloride in bulk and in pharmaceutical formulations. As UV-Visible spectrophotometer is a simple, low cost instrument, the developed method could be considered superior to the reported methods and attractive to routine pharmaceutical analysis.

Results and discussion

Different volumes of drug solution were taken into clean and dry volumetric flasks and maximum absorbance was measured at 209 nm against the blank. Methanol, 0.1 *N* HCl, acetone and water were tested to obtain the suitable solvent for analysis. Out of all the solvents, water was found to be suitable and shows reproducible absorbance maximum values.

The various aliquots of drug solutions in the range of 5–30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were taken and absorbance was measured at 209 nm. A calibration curve (Fig. 1) was constructed by plotting a graph between absorbance and concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$). The linearity of calibration graphs was proved by the high values of the correlation coefficient. The molar

Fig. 1. Calibration plot of selegiline hydrochloride.

absorbance and relative standard deviation percentage (%RSD) of response factors for proposed spectrophotometric method were calculated and presented in Table 1. The developed method was validated in terms of specificity, precision, linearity and accuracy. In the evaluation of the robustness, some parameters like drug concentration, wavelength range and shaking time were interchanged and found that the results remain unaffected. Method ruggedness was expressed in the terms of RSD% of the same procedure applied by two analysts and in two different instruments on different days. The results showed that no statistical difference between different analysts and instruments suggesting that the developed method was robust and rugged.

Table 1. Optical characteristics of proposed method

Parameter	Result
λ_{max} (nm)	209
Beer's law limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	5–30
Molar absorbance ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	2.264
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}/0.001 \text{ A.U.}$)	0.00119
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.9981
Slope (m)	0.0245
Intercept (c)	0.0966
%RSD	1.205
% Recovery	99.09 to 99.27%
LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1.387
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	4.203

The accuracy of an analytical method is the nearness in confirmity between the established exact value or reference value and the result obtained. The obtained results proved that the recovery values in bulk drug and in pharmaceutical forms were found within the acceptable boundary. Precision is a measure of the ability of a method to create reproducible results. It is evaluated using same concentration of sample by determining six times for repeatability, intermediate precision and reproducibility.

The intra-day and inter-day precisions were evaluated and results were reported in Table 2 and found %RSD was less than 2, which indicate that there was no significant difference for the intra-day and inter-day assay in bulk and pharmaceuticals formulations and found to be satisfactory. Recovery studies were carried out by adding different amounts of pure drug into the sample solution and five replicates of each concentration solution was measured. The mean recoveries were calculated and the results were presented in Table 3. The specificity and selectivity of the proposed method was evaluated by estimating the drug in presence of excipients such as starch, lactose and talc and found there is no interference from excipients present in the formulation.

Table 2. Evaluation of accuracy and precision results of the proposed method in bulk form

Name of the drug	Taken (mg/ml)	Intra-day			Inter-day		
		Found ^a	Recovery % \pm SD	% RSD	Found ^a	Recovery % \pm SD	% RSD
Selegiline hydrochloride	10	9.96	99.6 \pm 0.013	0.127	9.95	99.53 \pm 0.012	0.122
	20	19.97	99.86 \pm 0.007	0.038	19.96	99.78 \pm 0.010	0.052
	30	29.96	99.87 \pm 0.012	0.039	29.96	99.87 \pm 0.016	0.053

^aAverage of six determinations.

Table 3. Determination of recovery of selegiline hydrochloride in pharmaceutical formulation

Name of the drug	Pharmaceutical formulation	Labeled amount (mg/ml)	Found ^a (mg/ml)	Recovery % ± SD	% RSD
Selegiline hydrochloride	Selgin	5	4.96	99.27 ± 0.010	0.0216
	Elegelin	5	4.955	99.09 ± 0.017	0.0332
	Selerin	5	4.958	99.14 ± 0.019	0.0379

^aAverage of six determinations.

The limit of detection (LOD) of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value and the limit of quantitation (LOQ) is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy.

These were calculated using the following formulae.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \text{ s/S} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \text{ s/S} \quad (2)$$

where, s = standard deviation of the response and S = slope of the calibration curve.

The values of LOD and LOQ were presented in Table 1.

Experimental

A Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer (UV-160A) with a matched pair of 10 mm quartz cells are used for measuring the absorbance. Mettler Toledo analytical balance (accuracy 0.1 mg) was used for weighing all the samples.

Preparation of reagents and solutions :

Selegiline hydrochloride drug was obtained from M/s Malladi Drugs & Pharmaceuticals Limited, India, as a free sample and the tablets were purchased from M/s Intas Pharmaceuticals, Ahmadabad, M/s Sun Pharma and M/s Cipla, India. All chemicals used were of analytical grade. Double distilled water was used through the experiment. The standard stock solution of selegiline hydrochloride was prepared by taking accurately weighed 100 mg of drug. This is transferred into 100 ml standard flask, dissolved in distilled water to obtain the resulting solution's concentration as 1 mg/ml. The stock solution thus prepared was further diluted to obtain required concentrations for the present investigation.

Methods :

Proposed procedure for the determination of selegiline hydrochloride :

Different volumes of standard solution were transferred into a series of clean and dry standard flasks and made up to the mark with distilled water (5–30 µg/ml). The maximum absorbance of the solution was measured at 209 nm against the blank.

Analysis of pharmaceutical formulations :

10 tablets containing selegiline hydrochloride were taken, accurately weighed, finely grinded and mixed. 100 mg of powder was transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved in distilled water with the aid of sonication. The contents of the flask were made up to the mark, further diluted with distilled water to get required concentration. Before measuring the absorbance, the diluted solution was filtered through 0.45 µ membrane filter. The amount of the drug was estimated using calibration plot.

Conclusion

The developed UV spectrophotometric method is quite simple and do not require any pretreatment of the drug and tedious extraction procedure. The described procedure is reliable, accurate, rapid, cost effective and reproducible for estimation of selegiline hydrochloride in pharmaceutical formulations. Thus the developed method can be used for routine analysis of selegiline hydrochloride in bulk and in pharmaceutical formulations.

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